

Influence of Information and Communication Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of information and communication technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. The study was guided by three (3) objectives, three (4) research questions and three (4) hypotheses. The research adopted a cross-sectional survey design. The population of the study consisted of 285 staff of twenty-two (22) registered indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. All the 285 personnel in the twenty-two (22) registered indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State was studied through census sampling. The instrument used for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire titled “Influence of Information and Communication Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses Questionnaire (IICTJPIPHQ)”. The questionnaire was structured and validated by experts in the faculty of Education, Rivers State University. Reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha statistics which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.93 clusters. Mean values were used to answer the research questions, while Z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that there is a significant relationship between internet, email technology, computer technology and job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. It was concluded that internet, email technology, and computer technology significantly influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended amongst others that; Managers of Indigenous publishing houses should invest in reliable and high-speed internet connections to support seamless online operations. Also, collaborating with internet service providers to ensure uninterrupted connectivity can further enhance job performance.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Job Performance, Indigenous Publishing Houses

INTRODUCTION

Indigenous Publishing houses are specialized publishers that focus on producing and distributing books by indigenous authors. It could be defined as any publishing that is carried out by a joint Nigerian expatriate house where the Nigerian full participation is at least 5% (five percent) in terms of capital investment. They may be dedicated to a specific indigenous group or culture, or they may focus on a broader range of indigenous voices. This is to say that indigenous publishing is an entirely Nigerian house that is into publishing. Indigenous publishing houses play an important role in raising the profile of Indigenous materials in the publishing industry (Burrows, 2011). They do this through sharing Indigenous stories, supporting Indigenous writers and illustrators, and printing materials in Indigenous languages.

The last two decades had witnessed the global interaction and application of ICT facilities in the provision of information service delivery. Aina (2004) and Abubakar

(2010) remark that ICT is a term used to describe the items or equipment and computer programs that allow users to access, retrieve, store, organize, manipulate and present information of different kinds and for different purposes by electronic means. In effect, it embraces all the technologies that enable the handling of information and facilitate different forms of communication between man and electronic systems such as phones, computers, networks, radios, satellite systems among others. Apeh and Didiugwu (2016) opine that new technologies as manifested in information and communication technologies (ICT) include, personal computers, internet and World Wide Web have revolutionised book publishing operations and as well, turned the world into a global village. Information Technology via the internet is not only changing the way that we work, study, play and conduct our lives but is doing so much more quickly than any other notable revolution with impacts that are far more reaching than any other development (Osifeso,

2012). This revolution has transformed publishing processes from the analog to digital. Defleur and Dennis (2021:229) posit that Technology has been a mother for change that has driven publishing industries.

The internet is a worldwide network of inter-connected computer networks (commercial academic and government) that operates using a standardized set of communication protocols called TCP/IP (transmission control protocols/internets protocols) or the internet protocol suite. According to Gbaje (2007), Internet is a network of millions of computers linked together with telecommunication equipment for the purpose of sharing data, resources and information. Agbaje as cited in Uloaku (2017) sees Internet as a veritable tool for global online services. It is a mechanism for information dissemination and a medium for collaborative interaction between individuals and their computers. The Internet as a component of information and communication technologies provides a golden opportunity for the provision of value-added services by libraries. It is sufficed to state that the Internet is changing the traditional publishing firms and can enhance job performance of indigenous publishing houses.

Electronic mail (e-mail) is one of the services available through the internet. Electronic mail (e-mail) allows for creation and transmission of messages, which can be addressed to individuals or group of individuals (Nwokedi, Samuel & Amkpa, 2016). The recipient can access the message, respond to it, store it electronically, forward the message, print it or delete it. The major components of e-mail include ability to compose a message, address a message, send a message, send a message to multiple recipients, reply a message, forward a message, opening an attachment, print an item message, and retrieve a deleted message. These components of e-mail are very important for effective service delivery in book publishing houses, and can influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses.

Computer technology is a broad term that refers to the use of computers and other electronic devices to store, process, and communicate information. It includes things like hardware, software, networks, and data storage. It's often used to improve efficiency and productivity, and it has become an essential part of modern life. According to Ozioko (2005), computer is presently the best gift technology has presented to the

book publishers to improve it operations and services. It's used for things like word processing, layout and design, printing and distribution. Some publishers even use computer technology to market and promote their books. It is therefore that computers could influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses.

Afshan et al. (2012) define job performance as the achievement of specific tasks measured against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed. Job performance can be manifested in improvement in production, easiness in using the new technology, highly motivated workers". Many studies conducted earlier revealed that human resource management practices have been strongly and positively related to employee performance and developments areas. There has been a lot of research to support the fact that employee performance can improve through training by building a sense of teamwork among employees and to develop specialized financial skills. Job Performance is the successful completion of tasks by a selected individual or individuals, as set and measured by a supervisor or organization, to pre-defined acceptable standards while efficiently and effectively utilizing available resource within a changing environment.

Indigenous Publishing Houses are specialized publishers that focus on producing and distributing books by indigenous authors. They may be dedicated to a specific indigenous group or culture, or they may focus on a broader range of indigenous voices. In Nigeria, there are a few notable indigenous publishing houses. One example is Cassava Republic Press, which was founded in 2006 and is dedicated to promoting African writers and stories. Another example is Abiola's Publishers, which was established in 1992 and focuses on promoting Nigerian authors and stories. And one more example is Dakun Books, which publishes books about Yoruba culture, history, and language. Many indigenous publishing houses have a strong commitment to preserving indigenous languages and cultures, and they may also work to promote indigenous authors and stories. Arising from the above, it is therefore important to study the influence of Information and Communication Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Information and communication technology (ICT) has revolutionized the world and has brought about

tremendous change on every facet of life across the globe. It is an axiom that information technology since its emergence has turned the world to a global village. Information communication technology facilities are emerging technology which the publishing industry has keyed into, particularly the computer, internet, email and social media platforms. It is hardly possible to determine how ICT influences job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. This situation arises because there is hardly any empirical investigation that has dwelt on the influence of ICT on the performance of indigenous publishing houses. Although research works are carried out on publishing, they have been selective in nature and limited in focus. None has focused on the topic under study (Awoniyi, 2017; Adegoke, 2021). There is therefore observable neglect of the issue of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State which may lead to speculation on whether ICT plays any role on the job performance of the publishing houses. This is why this research is embarked upon to determine the influence of ICT on the job performance of indigenous publishing houses based on internet, computer, email and social media platforms.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the influence of information and communication technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. The specific objectives are to:

1. To determine the influence of internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.
2. To establish the influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.
3. To examine the influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.

Research Questions

Table 1: Population Distribution Table

S/N	Indigenous Publishing Houses in Rivers State	Staff	Management	Total
1	Allwell Publishers	8	4	12
2	Beckro Integrated Services Nigeria Limited	8	5	13
3	Biz Pages Nigeria Limited	10	5	15
4	Business Support Services	8	3	11
5	Danbru Digital Press	6	4	10
6	Detech Services	10	6	16
7	Hamiltons	10	5	15
8	Is-Jac International Company	9	3	12
9	Macmillian Nigeria Publishers Limited	10	4	14

In order to achieve the stated objectives, the following research questions will guide the study.

1. What is the influence of internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State?
2. What is the influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State?
3. What is the influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypothesis will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant influence of internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research, the researcher adopted the cross-sectional survey design. A cross-sectional survey is a type of observational research that analyzes data across a sample population at a specific point in time. In a cross-sectional study, the investigator measures the outcome and the exposures among the study participants at the same time (Singh, 2016). The study area was Rivers State. The population for the study is 285 staff of twenty-two (22) registered indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State (Obtained from the Yellow Pages Directory, Rivers State Ministry of Commerce & Industries). See below for the population distribution table.

10	Masterpiece Resources	8	4	12
11	Mediaprogetti Nigeria Limited	7	3	10
12	Minson Publishers	9	3	12
13	Nigerian Law Publications	11	3	14
14	Smart Publishing	10	4	14
15	Nsan Publishing House	10	3	13
16	Pearl Publishers	11	4	15
17	Rammy Wally Printing Press	10	2	12
18	Richgrip Publishers	10	4	14
19	Sonite Publishers Limited	8	3	11
20	Teams International Company Nigeria	9	3	12
21	Trumpet Press	9	4	13
22	Wolsman International Limited	10	5	15
	Total			285

Source: Yellow Pages Directory, Rivers State Ministry of Commerce & Industry

In this study, the research used all the 285 personnel in the twenty-two (22) registered indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State using census method. The entire population was adopted because it is manageable in terms of cost and accessibility. The instrument used in collecting data for this study was the Questionnaire. It is titled “Influence of Information and Communication Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses Questionnaire (ICTJPIPHQ)”.

The questionnaire was structured and was based on the research questions. The questionnaire was designed based on the modified 4-point Likert Rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The questionnaire was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A contains the demographic data of the respondents, while section B contains ICT factors on job performance by indigenous publishing houses.

The instrument is face and content validated by experts in Library and Information Science. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using the Cronbach Alpha

statistics. From the analysis, the alpha coefficient value for the items was 0.93. 285 (100%) copies of questionnaire were distributed to respondents, but 237 respondents representing 83.1% were returned while 48 respondents representing 16.8% were not returned. However, out of the 237 copies retrieved, 227 copies were correctly filled and used for data analysis. This therefore gives a response rate of 79.6%. Frequency tables and percentages were used to analyze the biodata of the respondents. Mean Values was used to analyze all the research questions based on item-by-item analysis. Each table of analysis produced a grand mean or significant mean with which each table was analyzed. Any item on each table with a mean value of 2.5 and above was considered high, while items with mean value below 2.5 was considered low. All the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. For the null hypotheses test, the decision rule was to reject the null hypothesis if the Z-statistic is greater than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the influence of internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Analyses of the Influence of Internet on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses

S/N	Questionnaire Items	SA	A	D	SD	N	Sum	Mean	Std.
1	I often use the internet to research topics for books publication	118	84	17	8	227	766	3.37	.773
2	I use online tools, such as translation software to assist with the translation of indigenous languages	78	134	10	5	227	739	3.26	.642
3	The use of internet to getting updated information regarding book publication	127	86	5	9	227	785	3.46	.730

4	My performance has increased as a result of Internet usage in book publication	119	84	19	5	227	771	3.40	.736
5	Internet has changed the way our organization promotes and sells books to customers	68	121	33	5	227	706	3.11	.723
6	We collaborate with authors, editors, and other publishing professionals through internet	96	61	41	29	227	678	2.99	1.058
7	The rise of e-books and digital publishing has affected our organization's sales and revenue	101	98	28		227	726	3.20	.950
Grand Mean								3.25	0.80

Source: Researcher Data/SPSS Output (2024)

The result on table 1 showed that the respondents agreed on all items on internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State with a mean score greater than 2.50 using a four-point Likert rating scale of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree. For instance, on the item of “The use of internet to getting updated information regarding book publication” majority of the respondents either agreed or agreed strongly, this shows that internet strongly

influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. The grand mean of 3.25 and standard deviation of 0.80 showed that the respondents strongly agreed that internet influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Analyses of the Influence of Email Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses

S/N	Questionnaire Items	SA	A	D	SD	N	Sum	Mean	Std.
8	I use email to communicate with editors, publishers, or other professionals involved in the book production process	96	93	25	13	227	726	3.20	.852
9	I use email to share drafts of book with other indigenous authors for feedback	108	94	20	5	227	759	3.34	.732
10	I use email to distribute books to readers or reviewers	159	34	9	25	227	781	3.44	.995
11	I use email to manage contracts, invoices, or other business documents related to the production of books	114	103	5	5	227	780	3.44	.651
12	The use of email technology influences the way our organization manages customer relationships and responds to customer inquiries	127	74	21	5	227	777	3.42	.751
								3.37	0.79

Source: Researcher Data/SPSS Output (2024)

The result on table 2 showed that the respondents agreed on all items on email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State with a mean score greater than 2.50 using a four-point Likert rating scale of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree. For instance, on the item of “I use email to manage contracts, invoices, or other business documents related to the production of books” majority of the respondents either agreed or agreed strongly, this shows that they use email to manage

contracts, invoices, or other business documents related to the production of books. The grand mean of 3.37 and standard deviation of 0.79 showed that the respondents strongly agreed that email technology influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Analyses of the influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses

S/N	Questionnaire Items	SA	A	D	SD	N	Sum	Mean	Std.
13	I use email to manage contracts, invoices, or other business documents related to the production of books	114	103	5	5	227	780	3.44	.651
14	I use computer software such as MS Word or Adobe in Design, to write and design books	138	43	29	17	227	756	3.33	.964
15	I use digital illustration or graphic design software to create images for books	126	54	42	5	227	755	3.33	.852
16	I use computer technology to format books for different platforms, such as print or ebooks	102	65	33	27	227	696	3.07	1.035
17	Computer technology has changed the way our organization stores and manages data related to book production, sales and inventory	127	86	5	9	227	785	3.46	.730
18	The use of computer technology influenced the way our organization markets and promotes books online	119	84	19	5	227	771	3.40	.736
								3.34	0.83

Source: Researcher Data/SPSS Output (2024)

The result on table 3 showed that the respondents agreed on all items on computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State with a mean score greater than 2.50 using a four-point Likert rating scale of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree. For instance, on the item of “I use computer technology to distribute books, such as sending digital files to a printing press” majority of the respondents either agreed strongly, this shows that they use computer technology to distribute books, such as sending digital files to a printing press. The grand mean of 3.38 and standard deviation of 0.83 showed that the

respondents strongly agreed that computer technology influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

The following hypothesis will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State

Table 4: z-test Result showing the significant influence of internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State

Test Value = 1						
t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
				Lower	Upper	
INTERNET	92.492	226	.000	12.48458	12.2186	12.7506

Source: Researcher Data/SPSS Output (2024)

The result on the Table 4 above showed that influence of internet significantly influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State with a z-test value of 61.767 and a degree of freedom of 226. Based on this result, the null hypothesis that stated the there is no significant influence of internet on job

performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State was rejected at 0.05 level of significance and the alternative hypothesis which stated that there is a significant influence of internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State was accepted.

H02: There is no significant influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.

Table 5: z-test Result Showing the Significant Influence of Email Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses in Rivers State

	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Email Technology	61.767	226	.000	11.41850	11.0542	11.7828

Source: Researcher Data/SPSS Output (2024)

The result on the Table 5 above showed that influence of email technology significantly influences job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State with a z-test value of 61.767 and a degree of freedom of 226. Based on this result, the null hypothesis that stated the there is no significant influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State was rejected at 0.05 level of

significance and the alternative hypothesis which stated that there is a significant influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State was accepted.

H03: There is no significant influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.

Table 6: z-test Result showing the Significant Influence of Computer Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses in Rivers State

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Computer Technology	53.773	226	.000	10.14537	9.7736	10.5172

Test Value = 3

Source: Researcher Data/SPSS Output (2024)

The result on the Table 6 above showed that influence of computer technology significantly influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State, with a z-test value of 53.773 and a degree of freedom of 226. Based on this result, the null hypothesis that stated the there is no significant influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State was rejected at 0.05 level of significance and the alternative hypothesis which stated that there is a significant influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State was accepted.

Rivers State. In support of the findings, Martyns (2021) investigated the application of Internet services for effective service delivery in university libraries in Plateau State. Findings of the study revealed that, the kinds of internet services applied for effective services delivery in university libraries in Plateau State include: Electronic Mail (email), World Wide Web (www), Internet Chat, Internet Telephone, Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), Electronic Library (e-library), Own Website, Web 2.0, Archie and Mailing list. The areas of application of internet services for effective library service delivery in university libraries in Plateau State include: acquisition services, cataloguing/classification services, awareness services, reference services, selective dissemination of information services, interlibrary loan services, documentary services, circulation services, bibliographic services and resource sharing.

Discussion of Findings

Influence of Internet on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses in Rivers State.

The result for the research questions 1, as shown in Table 2 above showed that the use of the internet influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. The result for the corresponding hypothesis also showed that there is a significant influence of internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in

Influence of Email Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses in Rivers State.

The result for the research questions 2, table 3 above showed that the use of email technology influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. Furthermore, the result for the corresponding hypothesis also showed that there is a significant influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. Nwokedi, Samuel and Amkpa (2016) determined the effects of E-mail Competence and Use on Service Delivery by Liberians in University Libraries in South East Zone of Nigeria. The following findings were made: the librarian's competence in e-mail as well as its use has a significant effect on their service delivery. This study is different from the present study as it adopted a descriptive design. However, the study will utilize the Pearson Product Moment Correlation in testing the relationship between information and communication technology and job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Influence of Computer Technology on Job Performance of Indigenous Publishing Houses in Rivers State.

The result for the research questions 3 as shown in Table 4 above showed that the use of computer technology influence job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. The result for the corresponding hypothesis also showed that there is a significant influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. In support of the findings, Aishat (2020) investigated the correlation between information communication technology and book production in publishing industry in Nigeria. Finding shows that, there was a significant relationship between the applications of communication and technology facilities in book production in Nigeria. The finding also revealed that, the publishers had accepted and adopted the use of communication and technology facilities in Nigeria publishing industry, and had improved quality of production and increased productivity of books.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that internet, email technology, computer technology and social media significantly influences job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. From results of the hypotheses, it was concluded that there is a significant influence of

internet on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. It was also concluded there is a significant influence of email technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. It was further concluded that there is a significant influence of computer technology on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State. It was finally concluded that there is a significant influence of social media on job performance of indigenous publishing houses in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results obtained from the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made, that:

1. Managers of Indigenous publishing houses should invest in reliable and high-speed internet connections to support seamless online operations. Collaborating with internet service providers to ensure uninterrupted connectivity can further enhance job performance.
2. Managers of Indigenous publishing should provide Regular training sessions on effective email management, communication etiquette, and the use of advanced email features should be conducted for employees. This can improve the efficiency and professionalism of communication within the organization.
3. Managers of Indigenous publishing also involve in Investing in modern and high-performance computers is crucial. Indigenous publishing houses should ensure that their hardware and software are up to date, enabling employees to work more efficiently and effectively.

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